

Adaptive opaque facades

Quantification of impacts on operational energy use

D4.9

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About the project

ZERAF is a disruptive facade concept (ZERo-carbon building enabler Adaptive opaque Facade technology), which aims to contribute to the necessary **drastic carbon footprint reduction of the EU building stock**.

To achieve a strong reduction of heating and cooling energy demand of buildings, **ZERAF concept shifts the opaque building facade systems from being static thermal barriers to thermal modulators**. Disruptive configurations of opaque facade technology and the use of innovative materials (smart Shape Memory Alloys, and new generation bio-based polyurethanes) enable such a dynamic thermal control. Moreover, ZERAF minimizes the number of primary sources (in terms of volume and diversity) and thus of the embodied carbon.

ZERAF radically reconceptualizes the adaptive opaque facades concept, taking the opportunity of doing **high-risk/low-TRL research in an interdisciplinary environment** to bring cutting edge novelties from aerospace, biomedicine, nanomaterials, chemistry and IOT to building sector.

The aim of the **EIC-EU funded project** is to scientifically prove that ZERAF concept **can control all heat transfer mechanisms in opaque building facades to a significant level**. Prototypes will be manufactured for the first time and their thermal behaviour will be characterized in a dedicated laboratory. To prove that used materials, fabrication processes and assembly methods do not jeopardize the carbon footprint reduction, most relevant sustainability parameters will be quantified through a building life cycle method.

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1 Executive Summary

This report presents deliverable D.4.9, focusing on the quantification of potential operational energy savings achieved by the ZERAF adaptive opaque façade technology through building-level energy simulations. This study evaluates the technology's impact compared to established benchmark façades across diverse European conditions, providing preliminary, non-validated results.

The assessment employed dynamic building energy simulations using three representative building archetypes (Single-Family House - SFH, Multi-Family House - MFH, and Office) derived from the IWG5 project. These models were simulated across six distinct European climates (Stockholm, Berlin, Bolzano, Milan, Athens, Madrid). ZERAF's performance was systematically compared against three passive envelope standards (Typical, Compliant, Gold) and two advanced passive façade concepts (Ventilated Façade variants and the INFINITE façade). Key metrics analyzed include annual heating, cooling, and total energy demand intensities (kWh/m²·year), supplemented by detailed hourly analysis of thermal performance during typical summer and winter weeks.

The simulation findings indicate that the ZERAF system consistently achieves the lowest total annual energy demand intensity across all climates for the SFH and MFH typologies, significantly outperforming even the highly insulated passive Gold standard. Reductions relative to the Typical baseline ranged from 82% to 93%, while savings compared to the Gold standard were particularly substantial in warmer climates (up to 66% further reduction in Athens) and still notable in colder climates (up to 39% further reduction in Bolzano). Crucially, unlike passive ventilated façades, which reduce cooling loads at the expense of increased heating demand, ZERAF demonstrated the ability to reduce both heating and cooling demands compared to the Gold standard, highlighting the benefit of active, adaptive control. In the Office archetype, where ZERAF was applied to a limited façade area, performance improvements over Gold were less pronounced but still consistently observed across all climates.

Detailed weekly analyses confirmed the synergistic operation of ZERAF's components. In summer, the combined action of KC (shading/ventilation) and ActIns (nighttime heat dissipation) led to lower indoor temperatures, reduced cooling peaks, and significantly lower cooling energy consumption compared to baseline conditions or the individual components operating alone. In winter, ZERAF effectively reduced heat loss through closed-loop active insulation (ActIns) and passive solar gain utilization (enabled by KC and ActIns), resulting in reduced heating demand and more stable indoor temperatures.

While these results strongly suggest significant energy-saving potential, they are preliminary and based on simulations. Key future work includes the experimental calibration of the specific KC and ActIns component models against laboratory data to increase confidence in their simulated behavior. Furthermore, optimization of the integrated control strategy is necessary, as analysis revealed specific conditions where performance could potentially be improved. Broadening the analysis to include realistic HVAC system interactions, optimizing ZERAF system control strategy, varying building thermal mass, diverse occupant behavior profiles, and performance under future climate scenarios will provide a more comprehensive assessment.

In conclusion, this simulation study provides compelling, albeit non-validated, evidence that the ZERAF active façade technology offers substantial potential for reducing building operational energy consumption across Europe, significantly surpassing the performance of both standard and advanced passive envelope solutions through its adaptive capabilities.

2 Introduction

2.1 Purpose of the Report

This report serves as a deliverable (T.4.1: Non-validated results at building level) for the ZERAF project. Its primary purpose is to quantify the potential impacts of the novel ZERAF adaptive façade technology on building operational energy use, making use of the methodology documented in D.2.1 [1].

Through detailed building energy simulations, this study aims to:

- **Quantify Energy Savings:** Estimate the reduction in annual heating and cooling energy demand (kWh/m²-year) achieved by implementing the ZERAF technology compared to conventional building envelope standards and defined benchmark façade technologies.
- **Benchmark Performance:** Compare ZERAF's performance against three standard conventional envelope performance levels (Typical, Compliant, Gold/Passivhaus) and two advanced passive façade systems (Ventilated Façade variants and INFINITE façade).
- **Assess Performance Across Climates and Contexts:** Evaluate the effectiveness of ZERAF across a range of European climates (Stockholm, Berlin, Bolzano, Milan, Athens, Madrid) and representative building typologies (Single-Family House, Multi-Family House, Office).
- **Provide Initial Insights:** Offer preliminary, non-validated quantitative results to understand the operational benefits and mechanisms of the ZERAF technology, informing future development, validation, and optimization efforts.

The findings presented herein provide a comparative assessment of ZERAF's energy-saving potential relative to established and alternative façade solutions under diverse climates and contexts.

2.2 Climates Used for the Study

To capture a broad spectrum of European climate conditions, six locations were chosen for simulation: Stockholm (Sweden), Berlin (Germany), Bolzano (Italy), Milan (Italy), Athens (Greece), and Madrid (Spain). These cities were deliberately selected to represent diverse climates across northern, central, and southern Europe, encompassing significant differences in heating and cooling requirements as well as solar irradiation levels.

Table 1 presents Heating Degree Days (HDD) (base temperature of 18° c), Cooling Degree Days (CDD) (base temperature of 21° C), and January solar irradiance for each climate. The HDD and CDD values reveal how some locations are predominantly heating-dominated (e.g., Stockholm, Bolzano, Berlin), while others experience substantial cooling loads (e.g., Athens, Madrid). January solar irradiance further illustrates wintertime solar gains, providing insight into how the sun can offset heating needs in colder climates.

Table 1. HDD, CDD, and January Solar Irradiance of Selected Climates. The color in each cell represents that specific climate's ranking among others.

Climate	Bolzano	Athens	Madrid	Berlin	Stockholm	Milan
Heating Degree Days	3,114	854	1,795	2,948	3,617	1,945
Cooling Degree Days	38	718	500	68	20	396
Jan. Solar Irradiance (kWh/m ²)	49.7	74.2	66.5	20.8	9.6	44.3

2.3 Three Performance Levels

Building codes and construction practices vary significantly across European countries, which could justify adjusting energy model parameters for each specific climate and location. However, to clearly understand and isolate how climate influences the relative performance between ZERAF and the benchmark façade technologies, the same base properties and performance criteria have been applied uniformly across all climates tested. In other words, regardless of whether a building is located in Berlin, Bolzano, Milan, Stockholm, Madrid, or Athens, each of the three building typologies (SFH, MFH, and Office) adopts a consistent set of assumptions for its Typical, Compliant, and Gold versions.

These three tiers capture a wide range of possible conditions, from older, less-efficient buildings to cutting-edge, high-performance envelopes aligned with more ambitious targets. By standardizing the building properties for each performance level across all climates, it becomes easier to isolate and compare how different façade technologies and climates influence energy use and occupant comfort.

Table 2 summarizes the R-values of primary building components for each performance tier. These values remain the same for the Single-Family House, Multi-Family House, and Office archetypes:

Table 2. R-values for Typical, Compliant, and Gold Building Components

BUILDING COMPONENT R VALUE M2.K/W	TYPICAL	COMPLIANT	GOLD (PASSIVE HOUSE)
EXTERNAL WALLS	0.5	3.33	6.67
ROOF	0.5	5.56	10
GROUND FLOOR	0.5	4	8.33
WINDOWS	0.33	0.83	1.25

- Typical:** Represents older, un-retrofitted buildings with poor insulation and windows. As a single "Typical" archetype cannot capture all construction variations across Europe, this level serves as a simplified, common benchmark of poor thermal performance (high U-values/infiltration). It provides a consistent baseline for measuring relative improvements within this study, acknowledging it's not nationally specific and could be refined in future regional research.

- **Compliant:** Reflects buildings meeting contemporary energy standards. The chosen targets are representative of demanding recent European national codes (based on German EnEV). This single, relatively high standard is applied uniformly across all climates to ensure fair comparisons, isolating the effects of climate and façade technology rather than varying national regulations.
- **Gold (Passivhaus):** Represents an advanced, low-energy construction level with highly insulated envelope components and high-performance glazing.

To achieve these performance levels in the simulations, specific multi-layer constructions were defined for the opaque elements. Table 3 details the layer composition for the external walls in each tier, referencing the materials whose properties are defined in Table 4.

Table 3. Modeled External Wall Construction Layers for Each Performance Level (Exterior to Interior).

PERFORMANCE LEVEL	LAYER 1	LAYER 2	LAYER 3	LAYER 4
TYPICAL	Exterior Finish	Minimal Insulation (Typical)	Brick	Interior Finish
COMPLIANT	Exterior Finish	Insulation (Compliant)	Brick	Interior Finish
GOLD	Exterior Finish	High-Perf. Insulation (Gold)	-	Interior Finish

The thermal properties assumed for the individual materials comprising these wall layers are provided in Table 4. Note that the exterior and interior finishing layers are consistent across all three performance levels.

Table 4. Thermal Properties of Materials Used in Typical, Compliant, and Gold Wall Constructions.

MATERIAL DESCRIPTION	THICKNESS (M)	CONDUCTIVITY (W/M·K)	DENSITY (KG/M ³)	SPECIFIC HEAT (J/KG·K)
EXTERIOR FINISH (RENDER/CLADDING)	0.02	0.70	2000	1090
MINIMAL INSULATION (TYPICAL)	0.03	0.20	30	1030
BRICK	0.15	0.77	1800	840
INSULATION (COMPLIANT)	0.095	0.03	43	1210
HIGH-PERFORMANCE INSULATION (GOLD)	0.18	0.03	40	1030
INTERIOR FINISH (PLASTER/BOARD)	0.013	0.16	1600	836

By using these standardized performance levels, the study ensures fair comparisons can be made across climates and typologies. This approach highlights the relative impact of façade technologies rather than confounding differences that might arise from region-specific code requirements.

3 Building Typology Energy Models

In order to assess the impact of the ZERAF technology at the building level, we adopted three representative building typologies, namely, a Single-Family House (SFH), a Multi-Family House (MFH), and an Office Building. These archetypes are taken from the IWG5 [2] project, which itself is grounded in prior studies such as TABULA [3] and INSPIRE [4].

IWG5 Archetype Selection:

“The IWG5 team identified three representative building archetypes (one single-family house, one multi-family house, and one office) for the studied climate zones to capture essential characteristics of existing European buildings. This approach builds on national building typologies developed in TABULA, ensuring that the chosen models reflect the building stock across Europe. To keep the simulations and analyses manageable, the project limited itself to three main geometries per climate zone.”

In this stage of the project, we used these IWG5 archetypes primarily for their well-defined building geometries, which reflect typical layouts, sizes, and configurations across Europe. In our study, we retained the original geometry while introducing modifications to thermal properties and other parameters that are relevant for determining energy performance: envelope assemblies, infiltration rates, occupant behavior, etc. This approach creates three distinct performance levels of Typical, Compliant, and Gold.

3.1 Residential Models (Single & Multi-Family Houses)

3.1.1 SFH and MFH Geometry and Layout

The SFH model represents a two-story residential dwelling (52m² per floor) with typical four-person family occupancy, while the MFH model represents three independent units within an apartment building, each one with a typical three-person family occupancy. The SFH and MFH geometry and layout information are outlined in Table 5.

Table 5. SFH and MFH geometry and layout [2]

Building archetypes	Building Geometry	
	Number of stories	2
	Building width/depth	8 m × 6.5 m
	Area per story	52 m ²
	Orientation	South
	Glazing ratio	South 20%, North 10%, West and East 12%
	Number of stories	3
	Building width/depth	16.4 m × 6.4 m
	Area per story	104.96 m ²
	Orientation	South
	Glazing ratio	South and North 20%, West and East no window

3.1.2 Residential Models Properties

The Single-Family House (SFH) and Multi-Family House (MFH) share common assumptions for occupancy, internal loads, ventilation, and heating/cooling (H/C) systems. These assumptions are adjusted to reflect three performance levels: Typical, Compliant, and Gold, as outlined in section 2.3. Table 6 summarizes the main parameters for each level.

Table 6. Residential Models: Key Assumptions Across Performance Levels

PARAMETER / CASE	TYPICAL	COMPLIANT	GOLD
CONSTRUCTION	Typical	Compliant	Gold
INFILTRATION RATE (ACH)	1	0.5	0.3
MECHANICAL VENTILATION (ACH)	N/A	0.5 when occupants present, 0.25 when not present- fresh air	0.5 when occupants present, 0.25 when not present- fresh air
HEAT RECOVERY	N/A	65% efficiency	75% efficiency
NATURAL VENTILATION (ACH)	1.0 (if Indoor Temp > 24°C and $\Delta T > 2^\circ\text{C}$, occupant present)	3.0 (if Indoor Temp > 24°C and $\Delta T > 2^\circ\text{C}$)	3.0 (if Indoor Temp > 24°C and $\Delta T > 2^\circ\text{C}$)
H/C SYSTEM	Ideal loads		
OCCUPANCY	Refer to the residential occupant schedule		
INTERNAL LOADS	Refer to the internal loads table		
SHADING CONTROL	Manual shading control - inside	Automated shading control - exterior	
LIGHTS W/M2	2	2	2

Mechanical Ventilation (ACH): In the Typical representative building, no mechanical ventilation system is installed, so fresh air is supplied only by infiltration and occupant-driven (natural) ventilation. The Compliant and Gold cases both include mechanical ventilation for a minimum supply of fresh air, equipped with heat recovery—more efficient in the Gold case—to reduce energy consumption.

Natural Ventilation (ACH): For the Typical building, windows are opened only under certain temperature conditions and only when occupants are present. In the Compliant and Gold cases, higher air change rates are possible thanks to an economizer function in the mechanical system, which complements any window ventilation by bringing in additional outdoor air when conditions are favorable.

Shading Control: Typical buildings rely on occupant action (manual). Therefore, they only operate whenever an occupant is present, whereas Compliant and Gold use automated exterior shading for more effective solar control.

H/C System: EnergyPlus' "Ideal loads" HVAC system is used to calculate the building loads.

Lights W/m²: A fixed lighting power density is applied in all performance levels to ensure a fair comparison and to prevent discrepancies in lighting heat gains from overshadowing the façade performance evaluation.

Internal Loads: The internal loads schedule for the residential typology models can be found in Table 7.

Table 7. Internal Loads table for the residential cases

TIME OF THE DAY	OCCUPANCY	INTERNAL LOADS (W/M ²)
DAYTIME	Occupied	4
	Unoccupied	1
NIGHTTIME		1
WEEKEND PEAK		4

3.1.3 Differences between SFH & MFH

While sharing the core assumptions outlined above, the primary difference between the SFH and MFH models in this study lies in the spatial and temporal distribution of occupancy, internal loads, and heating and cooling setpoints.

The MFH model represents a single-floor apartment unit. Occupancy, activities (internal loads), and comfort requirements are aggregated into a single profile for the entire dwelling unit, as detailed in Table 8.

Table 8. MFH: Occupancy Schedule (# occupants) and Heating/Cooling Setpoints (°C)

TIME PERIOD	WEEKDAYS OCCUPANTS	WEEKENDS OCCUPANTS	HEATING SETPOINT (°C)	COOLING SETPOINT (°C)
00:00 - 06:00	3	3	18.0	26
06:00 - 07:00	3	3	20.0	25
07:00 - 08:00	2	3	20.0	25
08:00 - 11:00	2	3	20.0	25
11:00 - 14:00	0	0	17.5	50 (Off)
14:00 - 18:00	2	3	20.0	25
18:00 - 19:00	3	3	20.0	25

19:00 - 20:00	2	3	20.0	25
20:00 - 21:00	2	3	20.0	26
21:00 - 22:00	3	2	20.0	26
22:00 - 23:00	3	3	20.0	26
23:00 - 24:00	3	3	18.0	26

The SFH model, being a two-story house, distributes occupancy and activities between the ground floor (SFH0 - living room, kitchen) and the first floor (SFH1 - bedrooms). This results in distinct schedules for each floor, reflecting daytime activity downstairs and nighttime occupancy upstairs. Table 9 and Table 10 detail these floor-specific schedules.

Table 9. SFH Ground Floor (SFH0): Occupancy Schedule (# occupants) and Heating/Cooling Setpoints (°C)

TIME PERIOD	WEEKDAYS OCCUPANTS	WEEKENDS OCCUPANTS	HEATING SETPOINT (°C)	COOLING SETPOINT (°C)
00:00 - 06:00	0	0	18.0	26
06:00 - 07:00	1	0	20.0	25
07:00 - 08:00	2	0	20.0	25
08:00 - 09:00	2	1	20.0	25
09:00 - 10:00	2	3	20.0	25
10:00 - 11:00	2	4	20.0	25
11:00 - 14:00	0	0	17.5	50 (Off)
14:00 - 18:00	2	4	20.0	25
18:00 - 19:00	4	4	20.0	25
19:00 - 20:00	2	4	20.0	25
20:00 - 21:00	2	3	20.0	25
21:00 - 22:00	2	2	20.0	25
22:00 - 23:00	1	1	20.0	25
23:00 - 24:00	0	0	18.0	26

Table 10. SFH First Floor (SFH1): Occupancy Schedule (# occupants) and Heating/Cooling Setpoints (°C)

TIME PERIOD	WEEKDAYS OCCUPANTS	WEEKENDS OCCUPANTS	HEATING SETPOINT (°C)	COOLING SETPOINT (°C)
00:00 - 06:00	4	4	18.0	26
06:00 - 07:00	3	4	20.0	25
07:00 - 08:00	2	4	20.0	25
08:00 - 09:00	0	3	17.5	50 (Off)
09:00 - 10:00	0	2	17.5	50 (Off)
10:00 - 19:00	0	0	17.5	50 (Off)
19:00 - 20:00	1	0	20.0	25
20:00 - 21:00	2	1	20.0	25
21:00 - 22:00	3	2	20.0	25
22:00 - 23:00	4	3	20.0	25
23:00 - 24:00	4	4	18.0	26

3.2 Office Model

3.2.1 Geometry and Layout

The office model represents a single-story, single-cell office zone (30m²) with three employees working with a typical office schedule. The office model is assumed to be located within a larger multi-story building. Consequently, only the south-facing façade is exposed to outdoor conditions and solar radiation. All other envelope components – the north, east, and west walls, as well as the floor and ceiling – are modeled as adiabatic surfaces. This assumes they border adjacent, similarly conditioned office spaces or zones, meaning no net heat transfer occurs across these internal boundaries. This configuration focuses the analysis primarily on the performance of the exterior south façade and its interaction with the internal environment. The office geometry and layout information is outlined in Table 11.

Table 11. Office Model geometry and layout [2]

Building archetypes	Building Geometry	
	Number of stories	1
	Building width/depth	3.6m × 8.2m
	Area per story	30 m ²
	Orientation	South
	Glazing ratio	South 40%

3.2.2 Office Model Properties

Similar to the residential models, the office model is evaluated across three performance levels: Typical, Compliant, and Gold, using the corresponding envelope R-values from Table 2 for the exposed wall and window. Table 12 outlines the key operational parameters specific to the office archetype.

Table 12. Office Model: Key Assumptions Across Performance Levels

PARAMETER / CASE	AVERAGE	COMPLIANT	GOLD
INFILTRATION RATE (ACH)	1	0.5	0.3
MECHANICAL VENTILATION (ACH)	1 (if Indoor Temp > 24°C and occupant present)	2 (if Indoor Temp > 24°C and $\Delta T > 2^\circ\text{C}$)	3 (if Indoor Temp > 24°C and $\Delta T > 2^\circ\text{C}$)
HEAT RECOVERY	N/A	70% efficiency	80% efficiency
NATURAL VENTILATION (ACH)	Integrated in the Mechanical Ventilation	N/A	
H/C SYSTEM	Ideal loads		
OCCUPANCY	Weekdays: three people from 9h to 18h		
INTERNAL LOADS	Refer to the office internal loads Table 13		
SHADING CONTROL	Manual shading control (glare or solar radiation > 300)	Automated shading control (glare or solar radiation > 300)	
LIGHTS W/M2	8	8	8

Ventilation Approach: The Typical case relies only on infiltration and assumed manual window opening for ventilation/cooling. Compliant and Gold cases have baseline mechanical ventilation for fresh air quality (with heat recovery) and a separate economizer function providing additional airflow for free cooling when beneficial, with increasing capacity/effectiveness from Compliant to Gold.

Shading: Trigger conditions (glare or solar radiation > 300 W/m²) are specified for both manual (Typical) and automated (Compliant/Gold) shading activation.

Table 13. Internal loads and heating/cooling setpoint temperatures table for the office case

TIME OF DAY	INTERNAL LOADS (W/M2)	HEATING SETPOINTS	COOLING SETPOINTS
WORK HOURS	8	21	25
NON-WORK HOURS	1	15	Off – Natural Ventilation on

4 Advanced Façade Model Application

In this section, the methodology for modeling the ZREAF technology and two other defined benchmark façade technologies, namely, Ventilated Façade and INFINITE, are explained. Throughout the methodology of this report, these advanced façade technologies were applied to the opaque parts of all buildings' envelope surfaces with outdoor boundary conditions.

4.1 ZERAF

The ZERAF technology was (Figure 1) modeled based on the deliverable D.2.1 of the project [1].

This method for modeling it enables the accurate representation of the closed-loop active insulation (ActIns) and the Kinetic Cladding (KC) and their dynamic behavior.

Figure 1. ZERAF technology shown in two different states: better thermal insulation (with KC closed and ActIns off) or higher thermal heat exchange (with KC opened and ActIns on).

4.2 Ventilated Façade

The Ventilated Façade technology (Figure 2) is an insulated construction with a high thermal mass in the interior layer, while a cladding on the exterior surface is placed at some distance to form a cavity, allowing ventilation for the exterior surface.

Figure 2. Schematic design of the Ventilated Façade.

This technology was modeled in two different variants, one for the Compliant performance level and another for the Gold performance level. In each variant, the construction is modeled in a way that its R-value matches the R-value of its corresponding performance level case, e.g., the Gold case building envelopes have the same R-value as the Ventilated Façade Gold. Both Ventilated Façade variants have a 10 cm concrete layer with 2240 kg/m³ density in their interior layer, and both have a cladding and a ventilated cavity with the same properties as the ZERAF's KC, though here, the cladding is static.

Based on the research literature, it is expected that the application of such a naturally ventilated cavity in front of the wall construction will reduce the building's cooling loads while at the expense of slightly increased heating loads [5]. This is because the cladding shades the opaque building surfaces and reflects a portion of the solar light, and the ventilation washes away the excessive heat collected in the cavity, keeping the building envelope cooler.

4.3 INFINITE

This façade technology is based on the prefabricated INFINITE façade technology shown in Figure 3 [6].

The full INFINITE concept envisions a highly module potentially incorporating features like active cladding, e.g., Building Integrated Photovoltaics (BIPV), building integrated solar thermal (BIST), or

green façades, embedded mechanical ventilation components (including heat recovery units and ductwork), and potentially hydronic elements for thermal energy storage or distribution.

Figure 3. INFINITE Façade technology.

However, for the purpose of this comparative energy assessment focused primarily on the passive and adaptive opaque envelope performance, several simplifications were made in its modeling:

Cladding: The potential operational energy impact of active cladding features (like electricity generation from BIPV or thermal energy from BIST) was not modeled. The outer cladding was simulated as a passive, static element with defined radiative properties, similar to the Ventilated Façade benchmark.

Integrated Systems: The detailed performance and energy consumption of embedded ventilation or hydronic systems were not explicitly modeled. Instead, the building's heating and cooling demands were calculated using EnergyPlus's "Ideal Loads Air System," which assumes perfect fulfillment of setpoints without modeling specific equipment.

Thermal Properties: To establish a fair comparison point related to the ZERAF system's baseline insulation, the INFINITE façade's thermal characteristics were modeled based on the ZERAF system with its ActIns fans permanently turned off and the KC represented as a permanent, static cladding (similar to the Ventilated Façade).

Based on the simulation methodology used in this study to model the ActIns component [7], the Active Insulation System in its inactive (fan off) state yields an effective R-value of approximately 5.40 m²·K/W. As the INFINITE façade is modeled based on this inactive ActIns state (combined with static cladding), its insulation level falls between the Compliant and Gold standards defined for this report. It should be noted, however, that this specific R-value stems from the modelling approach in [7] and is used here as the defining thermal resistance for the INFINITE façade benchmark to facilitate the interpretation of its comparative results.

4.4 Summary of Advanced façades model properties

To provide a clear overview of the specific construction build-ups and baseline thermal properties used for the advanced façade models evaluated in this study, the following tables summarize their layer compositions and key characteristics.

Table 14 details the layer-by-layer composition and the resulting nominal static thermal resistance (R-value) calculated for each configuration as modeled. Please note that the ventilated cavities and the claddings were not accounted for in calculating the thermal resistance. This table highlights the different materials and insulation thicknesses used.

Table 14. Modeled Construction Layers and Nominal Static Thermal Resistance (R-value) for the Advanced Façade Configurations.

ADVANCED FAÇADE	LAYER 1	LAYER 2	LAYER 3	LAYER 4	LAYER 5	LAYER 6	R-VALUE M ² .K/W
ZERAF	Limestone: 0.15m	Aluminum: 0.001m	BioPUR: 0.16m	Aluminum & finishing: 0.002m	Dynamic Cavity: 0.1m	Kinetic Cladding	5.4
INFINITE	Limestone: 0.15m	Aluminum: 0.001m	BioPUR: 0.16m	Aluminum & finishing: 0.002m	Static Cavity: 0.1m	Static Cladding	5.4
VENTILATED FAÇADE GOLD	Concrete 0.1m	Rockwool Insulation: 0.24	Static Cavity: 0.1m	Static Cladding	–	–	6.1
VENTILATED FAÇADE COMPLIANT	Concrete 0.1m	Rockwool Insulation: 0.14	Static Cavity: 0.1m	Static Cladding	–	–	3.4

The listed R-values represent the nominal static thermal resistance derived from the specified layers, used as a baseline for comparison. ZERAF and INFINITE share the same R-value (5.4 m²·K/W) which, for ZERAF, corresponds to its inactive state (ActIns off); its operational thermal performance is dynamic and variable. The Ventilated Façade R-values (3.4 and 6.1 m²·K/W) reflect the insulation levels designed for the Compliant and Gold benchmark variants, respectively. It is important to remember that while ZERAF features dynamic components (Cavity, Cladding, ActIns state), the INFINITE and Ventilated Façade models represent purely static configurations in these simulations.

The thermal properties assumed for the core materials used in the layers described in Table 14 are detailed in Table 15.

Table 15. Thermal Properties of Materials Used in Advanced Façade Construction Layers.

MATERIAL	THERMAL CONDUCTIVITY W/M/K	DENSITY KG/M ³	SPECIFIC HEAT J/KG/K
LIMESTONE	1	2000	840
ALUMINUM	237	2700	900
BIOPUR	0.033	30	1500
CONCRETE	1.7	2240	900
ROCKWOOL	0.04	100	1000

5 Results and Discussion

This section presents the findings of the simulation study, focusing on the annual heating and cooling energy demand intensities ($\text{kWh}/\text{m}^2\cdot\text{year}$) to quantify the operational energy performance impact of the ZERAF façade technology. To assess ZERAF's potential for energy savings and demand reduction, its performance is systematically compared against benchmarks across diverse European conditions. These benchmarks include standard (static) building envelope configurations representing three levels of performance scenario—Typical (Ty), Compliant (Co), and Gold (Go)—as well as defined benchmark advanced façade technologies, namely, Compliant and Gold Ventilated Façade variants (VCo, VGo) and the INFINITE façade (Inf). The analysis spans three representative building typologies (Single-Family House - SFH, Multi-Family House - MFH, and Office) simulated in six distinct European climates (Athens, Madrid, Milan, Bolzano, Stockholm, and Berlin).

5.1 Single Family House (SFH)

This subsection focuses specifically on the simulation results for the Single-Family House (SFH) archetype.

5.1.1 Benchmark Comparison: Typical, Compliant, Gold, and ZERAF

Figure 4 compares the annual heating and cooling energy demand intensities for four SFH variants—Typical (Ty), Compliant (Co), Gold (Go), and ZERAF (Z)—across six distinct European climates. The stacked bars in the figure represent the total energy demand for heating (orange) and cooling (blue), with percentage improvements shown relative to the Typical (Ty) case.

Figure 4. Heating and cooling energy demand intensity for SFH across six climates for Typical (Ty), Compliant (Co), Gold (Go), and ZERAF (Z). Bars show heating (orange) and cooling (blue), with indicated percentage improvements relative to the Typical (Ty) case.

The results demonstrate the substantial impact of improving the building envelope's thermal performance. Progressing from the Typical (Ty) to the Compliant (Co) and subsequently to the Gold (Go) performance level consistently leads to significant reductions in total energy demand intensity across all climates. These reductions, ranging from 65% (Athens, Compliant) to 87% (Bolzano, Gold), are primarily attributed to the progressively lower U-values of the opaque elements and windows, reduced air infiltration rates, and improved shading and ventilation control strategies implemented in the Compliant and Gold cases, as detailed in section 3.1.2.

The climate context significantly influences each case's energy demand profile. In colder climates, such as in Stockholm, Berlin, and Bolzano, heating demand constitutes the dominant portion of the total energy load. Conversely, in warmer climates like Athens, Madrid, and Milan, cooling demand represents a substantial portion, particularly for the less insulated Typical case. Improvements from Typical to Compliant and Gold effectively reduce both heating and cooling demands, though the relative magnitude of these reductions varies with climate. For instance, the transition from Ty to Co yields large heating savings in Stockholm (240 to 73 kWh/m²/year only heating energy) but also notable cooling savings in Athens (56 to 24 kWh/m²/year only cooling energy).

Critically, the ZERAF (Z) configuration consistently achieves the lowest total energy demand intensity among the four scenarios across all six climates. The percentage reductions relative to the Typical baseline are the highest for ZERAF in every location, reaching impressive levels of 86% in Stockholm to 93% in Madrid. Notably, ZERAF outperforms even the highly insulated Gold standard in terms of

total energy demand. This is significant, considering that the ZERAF system, when its Active Insulation System (ActIns) is inactive, possesses a nominal R-value (as represented by the INFINITE case, $R=5.4 \text{ m}^2\cdot\text{K}/\text{W}$) potentially lower than the Gold standard's opaque wall ($R=1/0.15 = 6.67 \text{ m}^2\cdot\text{K}/\text{W}$). This highlights the substantial energy-saving potential unlocked by the *activation* of the façade, i.e., Kinetic Cladding (KC) and Active Insulation System (ActIns), compared to purely passive envelope strategies.

While ZERAF demonstrates superior performance universally, the magnitude of its advantage over the Gold standard varies. The difference is particularly pronounced in climates with significant cooling loads (Athens, Madrid, Milan). In these locations, ZERAF achieves total energy savings ranging from 90% to 93% compared to the Typical case, surpassing the Gold standard's savings (71% to 84%). This suggests that ZERAF's active heat rejection capabilities via KC (solar radiation reflection and natural ventilation of the cavities) and its active heat dissipation capabilities via ActIns (increased heat transfer through the envelope during nighttime) are especially beneficial in mitigating cooling demands.

In the meantime, ZERAF achieves notable heating demand reduction in climates with higher solar irradiance in their heating period, e.g., Bolzano and Madrid. This suggests that ZERAF's passive heating capability via ActIns (increased heat transfer through the envelope to let in the absorbed solar heat on the opaque surfaces) is beneficial in mitigating heating demands. The specific mechanisms contributing to ZERAF's performance are explored further in the subsequent sections.

5.1.2 Advanced Façades Comparison in Warmer Climates

To further investigate the performance differences among advanced façade solutions, Figure 5 focuses on the warmer climates—Athens, Madrid, and Milan—where cooling demand is a significant factor. This figure compares the annual heating and cooling energy demand intensities for six SFH configurations: Compliant (Co), Ventilated Façade Compliant (VCo), Gold (Go), Ventilated Façade Gold (VGo), INFINITE (Inf), and ZERAF (Z). Percentage values indicate the change in total energy demand relative to the corresponding passive baseline (Co for VCo; Go for VGo, Inf, and Z).

Figure 5. Heating and cooling energy demand intensity for SFH in warmer climates (Athens, Madrid, Milan) for Compliant (Co), Ventilated Façade Compliant (VCo), Gold (Go), Ventilated Façade Gold (VGo), INFINITE (Inf), and ZERAF (Z). Bars show heating (orange) and cooling (blue), with percentage improvements referenced against the Compliant (Co) baseline.

The introduction of a passive Ventilated Façade (VF) system, both in its Compliant (VCo) and Gold (VGo) variants, demonstrates the expected trade-off: a reduction in cooling demand accompanied by an increase in heating demand compared to their respective non-ventilated baselines (Co and Go). This effect is attributed to the ventilated cavity reducing direct solar gain absorption by the main wall via shading from the cladding and convective heat removal within the cavity [5].

In Athens, the VGo configuration (Total: 20.7 kWh/m²/yr) also yields a substantial net benefit compared to Go (Total: 25.9 kWh/m²/yr), achieving a 20% reduction in total energy, driven by a large cooling decrease (from 24.0 to 18.5 kWh/m²/yr) that outweighs a small heating increase (from 1.9 to 2.2 kWh/m²/yr).

In Madrid, transitioning from Go (Total: 18.5 kWh/m²/yr) to VGo (Total: 15.3 kWh/m²/yr) reduces cooling demand by 38% (from 11.9 to 7.4 kWh/m²/yr) while increasing heating demand by 20% (from 6.6 to 7.9 kWh/m²/yr). The net effect is a significant 17% reduction in total energy demand relative to the Gold baseline.

Similarly, in Milan, the VGo configuration increases heating demand (14.8 vs Go 12.8 kWh/m²/yr, an increase of 2.0 kWh/m²/yr) while substantially decreasing cooling demand (8.9 vs Go 13.6 kWh/m²/yr, a saving of 4.7 kWh/m²/yr). Like the other two cases, the cooling savings outweigh the heating penalty, resulting in a net decrease in total energy demand from 26.4 kWh/m²/yr (Go) to 23.7 kWh/m²/yr (VGo).

This represents a 10% reduction relative to the Gold baseline (note: this calculated percentage differs from visual graph labels).

Overall, the passive VF demonstrates a net energy benefit in these warmer climates, primarily due to significant cooling load reductions.

The INFINITE (Inf) façade, being equivalent to a ZERAF system with inactive ActIns ($R \approx 5.4 \text{ m}^2 \cdot \text{K/W}$) and static cladding, also benefits from the passive ventilation effect. Compared to the Gold standard (Go, $R \approx 6.67 \text{ m}^2 \cdot \text{K/W}$), INFINITE exhibits lower cooling demands in all three cities (e.g., Madrid: 7.5 vs 11.9 kWh/m²/yr) but higher heating demands (e.g., Madrid: 8.8 vs 6.6 kWh/m²/yr), attributed to the combined effect of the cavity and its slightly lower insulation level. Critically, the net effect on total energy demand shows an improvement over the Gold standard in these warmer climates:

- Athens: INFINITE (21.2 kWh/m²/yr) achieves an 18% reduction vs Gold (25.9 kWh/m²/yr).
- Madrid: INFINITE (16.3 kWh/m²/yr) achieves a 12% reduction vs Gold (18.5 kWh/m²/yr).
- Milan: INFINITE (25.0 kWh/m²/yr) achieves a 5% reduction vs Gold (26.4 kWh/m²/yr).

This indicates that even the passive cavity effect, despite a slightly lower nominal R-value, provides a net annual energy benefit compared to the highly insulated static Gold façade in these cooling-influenced environments.

Most significantly, the ZERAF (Z) system demonstrates exceptional performance, achieving the lowest total energy demand intensity among all configurations in these warmer climates (Athens: 8.8, Madrid: 7.4, Milan: 12.7 kWh/m²/yr). Unlike the passive strategies, ZERAF's active control capabilities enable it to substantially reduce both heating and cooling demands compared to the Gold standard.

ZERAF achieves significant cooling load reductions compared to Gold: 68% in Athens (7.7 vs 24.0), 74% in Madrid (3.1 vs 11.9), and 74% in Milan (3.5 vs 13.6 kWh/m²/yr). This highlights the effectiveness of the dynamically controlled KC (providing optimal shading/ventilation during high solar gain periods) potentially coupled with the ActIns facilitating active heat rejection from the building envelope during suitable (e.g., nighttime) conditions.

Simultaneously, ZERAF lowers heating demands compared to Gold: 42% in Athens (1.1 vs 1.9), 35% in Madrid (4.3 vs 6.6), and 28% in Milan (9.2 vs 12.8 kWh/m²/yr). This suggests the system effectively adapts during cooler periods, maximizing insulation via ActIns control and managing the KC to either trap solar gains or minimize losses, thus avoiding the heating penalties seen with passive cavities.

The combined effect leads to substantial total energy savings relative to the already efficient Gold standard: -66% in Athens, -60% in Madrid, and -52% in Milan. This underscores the transformative potential of active façade management, leveraging synergistic control of kinetic shading/ventilation and dynamic insulation to optimize performance across varying conditions.

In summary, while passive ventilated façades (VGo, Inf) offer net energy benefits over standard high-performance façades (Go) in these warmer climates by significantly reducing cooling loads, they still incur heating penalties. The ZERAF system, through its integrated active control of KC and ActIns, overcomes this limitation, delivering superior performance by substantially reducing both heating and cooling demands, leading to the lowest overall energy demand.

5.1.3 Advanced Façades Comparison in Colder Climates

Figure 6 provides a comparative analysis of the advanced façade configurations—Compliant (Co), Ventilated Façade Compliant (VCo), Gold (Go), Ventilated Façade Gold (VGo), INFINITE (Inf), and ZERAF (Z)—within the colder, heating-dominated climates of Bolzano, Stockholm, and Berlin. The percentage changes shown on the bars represent the change in total annual energy demand intensity relative to the Co case.

Figure 6. Heating and cooling energy demand intensity for SFH in colder climates (Bolzano, Stockholm, Berlin) for Compliant (Co), Ventilated Façade Compliant (VCo), Gold (Go), Ventilated Façade Gold (VGo), INFINITE (Inf), and ZERAF (Z). Bars show heating (orange) and cooling (blue), with percentage improvements referenced against the Compliant (Co) baseline.

In these climates, heating loads overwhelmingly dominate the annual energy balance (e.g., Stockholm Go: Heating 34.8 kWh/m²/yr, Cooling 0.9 kWh/m²/yr; Berlin Go: Heating 26.4 kWh/m²/yr, Cooling 2.2 kWh/m²/yr). Cooling demand is minimal across all configurations. Consequently, the impact of introducing a passive ventilated cavity (VCo, VGo, Inf) has a negative impact on overall energy performance. While these systems effectively eliminate the already small cooling loads, they induce a substantial penalty in the form of increased heating demand compared to their non-ventilated counterparts (Co and Go). The continuous air movement within the cavity, beneficial for heat rejection in summer, significantly promotes convective heat loss during the prolonged cold heating season.

This results in higher total energy demand intensities for the passive ventilated systems:

Compared to the Gold baseline (Go), the VGo configuration shows an increase in total energy demand of 12% in Bolzano (25.2 vs 22.5 kWh/m²/yr), 8% in Stockholm (38.5 vs 35.7 kWh/m²/yr), and 5% in Berlin (29.9 vs 28.6 kWh/m²/yr).

Similarly, the INFINITE façade (Inf), with its passive cavity and R-value between Compliant and Gold, performs worse than the Gold standard in all three cold climates, increasing total energy demand by 21% in Bolzano (27.3 vs 22.5 kWh/m²/yr), 14% in Stockholm (40.8 vs 35.7 kWh/m²/yr), and 11% in Berlin (31.8 vs 28.6 kWh/m²/yr).

The VCo also shows increased total demand relative to Co (+15% in Bolzano, +9% in Stockholm, +7% in Berlin). This indicates that passive ventilated façades lead to increased annual energy consumption in strongly heating-dominated European climates.

In contrast, the ZERAF (Z) system again achieves the lowest total energy demand intensity in all three colder climates (Bolzano: 13.8, Stockholm: 33.9, Berlin: 25.7 kWh/m²/yr). It not only minimizes the negligible cooling loads but, crucially, also achieves reductions in the dominant heating demand compared to the highly insulated Gold standard:

- Bolzano: Heating reduced by 35% (13.6 vs 21.0 kWh/m²/yr)
- Stockholm: Heating reduced by 3% (33.7 vs 34.8 kWh/m²/yr)
- Berlin: Heating reduced by 5% (25.2 vs 26.4 kWh/m²/yr)

This superior performance highlights ZERAF's adaptive capability. During cold periods, the Active Insulation System (ActIns) can be controlled to maximize thermal resistance, minimizing conductive losses. Simultaneously, the Kinetic Cladding (KC) can be managed dynamically – closing to create a more insulating stagnant air layer and reduce radiative/convective losses to the environment, or opening during sunny winter days to allow solar radiation to reach the opaque wall, with the ActIns then facilitating the transfer of this captured heat inward [7]. This active management prevents the significant heating penalties incurred by the continuously vented passive systems.

The extent of the heating and total energy reduction achieved by ZERAF relative to the Gold standard varies notably with climate, correlating strongly with winter solar irradiance levels (Table 1: Jan Solar Irradiance kWh/m²).

- In Bolzano, with relatively high winter solar irradiance (49.7), ZERAF achieves a substantial 39% reduction in total energy demand compared to Gold (13.8 vs 22.5 kWh/m²/yr).
- In Berlin, with moderate winter irradiance (20.8), ZERAF provides a 10% reduction in total energy compared to Gold (25.7 vs 28.6 kWh/m²/yr).
- In Stockholm, characterized by very low winter solar irradiance (9.6), the total energy reduction compared to Gold is smaller, at 5% (33.9 vs 35.7 kWh/m²/yr).

In summary, for the SFH typology in colder climates, passive ventilated façades (VCo, VGo, INFINITE) are counterproductive, increasing total energy consumption due to elevated heating loads. The actively controlled ZERAF system, however, successfully avoids this penalty and delivers the best overall performance. It achieves this by reducing heating demand relative to the Gold standard – a benefit whose magnitude is linked to the solar radiation availability in the heating period – while also effectively eliminating residual cooling loads.

5.1.4 Single-Family House Results Conclusion

In summary, for the Single-Family House typology, simulations demonstrate substantial energy savings progressing from the Typical to the Gold standard passive envelopes. However, the actively controlled ZERAF system consistently delivered the lowest total annual energy demand across all climates, significantly outperforming even the highly insulated Gold standard. Compared to advanced passive strategies, ZERAF proved superior:

In warmer climates, passive ventilated façades (VGo, INFINITE) offered net energy benefits over Gold by reducing cooling loads but incurred heating penalties. ZERAF overcame this limitation, drastically reducing both heating and cooling demands.

In colder climates, passive ventilated façades were detrimental, increasing total energy use compared to Gold due to significant heating penalties. ZERAF successfully avoided these penalties, instead reducing heating loads relative to Gold, with the benefit correlating positively with winter solar availability.

Overall, the ZERAF system's active management of heat flows via its Kinetic Cladding and Active Insulation allows it to adapt effectively to diverse conditions, achieving energy performance beyond the capabilities of even advanced passive façade solutions for the SFH archetype.

5.2 Multi Family House (MFH)

This subsection details the simulation results for the Multi-Family House (MFH) archetype, following the same comparative structure used for the SFH. The MFH generally exhibits lower energy demand intensities compared to the SFH due to a more favorable surface-area-to-volume ratio and more shared floors and ceilings reducing overall heat loss/gain.

5.2.1 Benchmark Comparison: Typical, Compliant, Gold, and ZERAF

Figure 7 illustrates the annual heating and cooling energy demand intensities for the MFH across the six European climates, comparing the Typical (Ty), Compliant (Co), Gold (Go), and ZERAF (Z) envelope performance levels. Stacked bars represent heating (orange) and cooling (blue) demands, with percentage values showing the total energy demand reduction relative to the Typical (Ty) baseline.

Figure 7. Heating and cooling energy demand intensity for MFH across six climates for Typical (Ty), Compliant (Co), Gold (Go), and ZERAF (Z). Bars show heating (orange) and cooling (blue), with indicated percentage improvements relative to the Typical (Ty) case.

Similar to the SFH, improving the MFH envelope and other thermal properties from Typical to Compliant and Gold standards yields substantial reductions in total energy demand across all climates. For example, in Berlin, total demand decreases from 158.5 kWh/m²/yr (Ty) to 54.0 kWh/m²/yr (Co) and further to 27.7 kWh/m²/yr (Go). These improvements, reaching up to an 83% reduction for Gold relative to Typical (e.g., Bolzano, Berlin), stem directly from enhanced insulation, reduced infiltration, and better control strategies defined for the Compliant and Gold levels.

As before, climate dictates the energy profile: Stockholm (Ty Total: 181.3 kWh/m²/yr), Berlin (Ty Total: 158.5 kWh/m²/yr), and Bolzano (Ty Total: 139.9 kWh/m²/yr) remain heating-dominated. Athens (Ty Cooling: 53.4 vs Heating: 25.3 kWh/m²/yr), Madrid (Ty Cooling: 33.4 vs Heating: 65.8 kWh/m²/yr), and Milan (Ty Cooling: 33.3 vs Heating: 83.7 kWh/m²/yr) show significant cooling dominated, especially in the less efficient Typical case.

The ZERAF (Z) configuration consistently achieves the lowest total energy demand intensity for the MFH in all six climates, with demands ranging from just 7.9 kWh/m²/yr (Athens) to 32.3 kWh/m²/yr (Stockholm). The total energy reductions relative to the Typical baseline are the highest for ZERAF, ranging from 82% (Stockholm) to 91% (Madrid). ZERAF significantly outperforms the passive Gold standard in every climate. The additional reduction achieved by ZERAF compared to Gold is particularly substantial in warmer climates:

- Athens: 57% further reduction (7.9 vs 18.5 kWh/m²/yr)
- Madrid: 47% further reduction (8.9 vs 16.7 kWh/m²/yr)

- Milan: 52% further reduction (13.6 vs 22.6 kWh/m²/yr)

In colder climates, the gains over Gold are still notable:

- Bolzano: 25% further reduction (17.5 vs 23.4 kWh/m²/yr)
- Stockholm: 4% further reduction (32.3 vs 33.7 kWh/m²/yr)
- Berlin: 8% further reduction (25.6 vs 27.7 kWh/m²/yr)

This superior performance across diverse conditions confirms the effectiveness of ZERAF's active adaptation via its Kinetic Cladding (KC) and Active Insulation System (ActIns), enabling energy optimization beyond the capabilities of high-performance passive envelopes.

5.2.2 Advanced Façades Comparison in Warmer Climates

Figure 8 isolates the warmer climates—Athens, Madrid, and Milan—to compare the performance of Compliant (Co), Ventilated Façade Compliant (VCo), Gold (Go), Ventilated Façade Gold (VGo), INFINITE (Inf), and ZERAF (Z) configurations for the MFH. Percentage values denote the change in total energy demand relative to the Compliant (Co) baseline.

Figure 8. Heating and cooling energy demand intensity for MFH in warmer climates (Athens, Madrid, Milan) for Compliant (Co), Ventilated Façade Compliant (VCo), Gold (Go), Ventilated Façade Gold (VGo), INFINITE (Inf), and ZERAF (Z). Bars show heating (orange) and cooling (blue), with percentage improvements referenced against the Compliant (Co) baseline.

Similar to the SFH results, the passive Ventilated Façade systems (VCo, VGo) demonstrate the previously discussed lower-cooling-higher-heating trade-off. Compared to their non-ventilated counterparts, they reduce cooling loads but increase heating loads.

The VCo configuration shows marginal changes in total energy demand relative to Co: -10% in Athens (23.2 vs 25.9 kWh/m²/yr), +3% in Madrid (31.3 vs 30.3 kWh/m²/yr), and 0% in Milan (39.8 vs 39.6 kWh/m²/yr). The cooling savings are often offset by the heating penalty.

The VGo configuration, compared to the Gold standard (Go), reduces cooling (e.g., Madrid: 4.5 vs 7.1 kWh/m²/yr) but increases heating (e.g., Madrid: 10.4 vs 9.6 kWh/m²/yr). The net effect relative to the Compliant (Co) baseline is a significant reduction in total energy: -28% in Athens (15.5 vs 25.9 kWh/m²/yr), -50% in Madrid (14.9 vs 30.3 kWh/m²/yr), and -46% in Milan (21.0 vs 39.6 kWh/m²/yr). This highlights that VGo, despite its internal trade-off compared to Go, represents a substantial improvement over the Compliant standard.

The INFINITE (Inf) façade also provides considerable savings compared to the Compliant (Co) baseline, achieving total energy reductions of -38% in Athens (15.8 vs 25.9 kWh/m²/yr), -48% in Madrid (15.7 vs 30.3 kWh/m²/yr), and -44% in Milan (22.1 vs 39.6 kWh/m²/yr). Compared to the Gold standard (Go), INFINITE exhibits slightly higher heating (e.g., Madrid: 11.2 vs 9.6) but lower cooling (e.g., Madrid: 4.5 vs 7.1), resulting in similar total energy demands (Athens: Inf 15.8 vs Go 18.5; Madrid: Inf 15.7 vs Go 16.7; Milan: Inf 22.1 vs Go 22.6).

ZERAF (Z), however, demonstrates outstanding performance, yielding the lowest energy demands by far. Relative to the Compliant (Co) baseline, ZERAF achieves total energy reductions of -69% in Athens (7.9 vs 25.9 kWh/m²/yr), -70% in Madrid (8.9 vs 30.3 kWh/m²/yr), and -65% in Milan (13.6 vs 39.6 kWh/m²/yr). Critically, ZERAF reduces both heating and cooling loads compared to the Gold (Go) standard:

- Heating Reduction (Z vs Go): Athens (-34%), Madrid (-26%), Milan (-18%).
- Cooling Reduction (Z vs Go): Athens (-63%), Madrid (-75%), Milan (-76%).

This dual benefit, achieved through active KC management (shading/ventilation) and ActIns operation (nighttime heat dissipation and heating season passive heating), distinguishes ZERAF from passive strategies involving fixed ventilation or insulation levels.

5.2.3 Advanced Façades Comparison in Colder Climates

Figure 9 examines the advanced façade configurations in the colder, heating-dominated climates of Bolzano, Stockholm, and Berlin for the MFH. Percentage changes are referenced against the Compliant (Co) baseline.

Figure 9. Heating and cooling energy demand intensity for MFH in colder climates (Bolzano, Stockholm, Berlin) for Compliant (Co), Ventilated Façade Compliant (VCo), Gold (Go), Ventilated Façade Gold (VGo), INFINITE (Inf), and ZERAF (Z). Bars show heating (orange) and cooling (blue), with percentage improvements referenced against the Compliant (Co) baseline.

In these climates, where heating constitutes nearly the entire energy load, passive ventilation proves disadvantageous for annual energy performance.

The VCo configuration results in higher total energy demand compared to Co due to increased heating loads: +12% in Bolzano (55.9 vs 49.5 kWh/m²/yr), +7% in Stockholm (70.1 vs 65.2 kWh/m²/yr), and +5% in Berlin (57.0 vs 54.0 kWh/m²/yr).

The VGo configuration, while better than Co (-48% Bolzano, -45% Stockholm, -47% Berlin relative to Co), performs slightly worse than the standard Gold (Go) configuration due to increased heating penalties: +8% total energy in Bolzano (25.6 vs 23.4), +6% in Stockholm (35.7 vs 33.7), +4% in Berlin (28.5 vs 27.7).

The INFINITE (Inf) façade also shows increased total energy demand compared to Gold: +17% in Bolzano (27.3 vs 23.4), +12% in Stockholm (37.5 vs 33.7), and +7% in Berlin (30.0 vs 27.7). Its savings relative to Co (-44% Bolzano, -42% Stockholm, -44% Berlin) are less than those achieved by Gold.

These results confirm that the heat loss associated with passive cavities outweighs any minimal cooling benefits in these heating-dominated climates for the MFH.

ZERAF (Z) again stands out as the top performer, achieving the lowest total energy demands (Bolzano: 17.5, Stockholm: 32.3, Berlin: 25.6 kWh/m²/yr). It yields significant reductions relative to the

Compliant (Co) baseline: -64% in Bolzano, -50% in Stockholm, and -52% in Berlin. More importantly, ZERAF also reduces heating demand compared to the passive Gold standard:

- Bolzano: Heating reduced by 23% (17.4 vs 22.6 kWh/m²/yr)
- Stockholm: Heating reduced by 3% (32.3 vs 33.2 kWh/m²/yr)
- Berlin: Heating reduced by 4% (25.4 vs 26.4 kWh/m²/yr)

The active control mechanisms of ZERAF—optimizing insulation value via ActIns and managing solar gains or minimizing losses via KC—allow it to avoid the heating penalties of passive cavities while further improving upon the Gold standard. The magnitude of improvement over Gold correlates with winter solar availability:

Total Energy Reduction (Z vs Go): Bolzano (25%) > Berlin (8%) > Stockholm (4%).

This reinforces the observation that ZERAF's ability to actively utilize solar gains contributes significantly to its superior performance in heating-dominated climates with available winter sun.

In conclusion for the MFH, ZERAF consistently delivers the highest energy savings across all climates and scenarios, demonstrating substantial improvements over both standard practices and advanced passive façade technologies by actively managing heat flows through dynamic insulation and kinetic cladding control.

5.2.4 Multi-Family House Results Conclusion

The simulation results for the Multi-Family House archetype largely mirror the findings for the SFH, confirming the effectiveness of the ZERAF technology. Standard envelope improvements (Typical to Gold) yielded significant energy reductions. Among all tested configurations, ZERAF consistently achieved the lowest total annual energy demand intensity in all six climates, substantially outperforming the passive Gold standard. Key comparisons reveal:

In warmer climates, while passive ventilated façades (VGo, INFINITE) showed some net benefit over Gold by mitigating cooling loads (despite increasing heating), ZERAF provided far greater savings by reducing both heating and cooling demands significantly.

In colder climates, passive ventilated façades again proved counterproductive, increasing total energy consumption relative to Gold due to elevated heating losses. In contrast, ZERAF avoided this penalty and achieved further heating energy reductions compared to the Gold standard, particularly benefiting from available winter solar radiation.

In conclusion for the MFH typology, ZERAF's integrated active control of KC and ActIns consistently delivers superior energy performance across diverse European climates, demonstrating significant advantages over both standard high-performance passive envelopes and advanced passive ventilated façade technologies.

5.3 Office

This subsection analyzes the energy performance simulation results for the Office building archetype. As detailed in Section 2.2, this model represents an office space within a larger building, where only the south-facing glazed wall is exposed to the exterior environment; other envelope components are

adiabatic. Consequently, the advanced façade technologies (VCo, VGo, Inf, Z) are applied only to the opaque portion of this single exterior wall. This limited application area inherently restricts the overall impact these technologies can have on the building's total energy demand compared to the SFH and MFH cases where they were applied to all exterior opaque surfaces.

5.3.1 Benchmark Comparison: Typical, Compliant, Gold, and ZERAF

Figure 10 displays the annual heating (orange) and cooling (blue) energy demand intensities for the Office archetype across the six climates, comparing the Typical (Ty), Compliant (Co), Gold (Go), and ZERAF (Z) scenarios. Percentage values indicate the total energy demand reduction achieved relative to the Typical (Ty) baseline.

Figure 10. Heating and cooling energy demand intensity for Office across six climates for Typical (Ty), Compliant (Co), Gold (Go), and ZERAF (Z). Bars show heating (orange) and cooling (blue), with indicated percentage improvements relative to the Typical (Ty) case.

Here, in heating-dominated climates like Stockholm and Berlin, improving insulation significantly cuts heating loads (e.g., Berlin Ty H: 45.0 -> Go H: 3.2 kWh/m²/yr).

In cooling-dominated climates like Athens, improvements primarily reduce the substantial cooling load (Ty C: 58.1 -> Go C: 35.3 kWh/m²/yr), though heating loads are already minimal.

Mixed climates like Milan and Bolzano see reductions in both heating and cooling.

Like before, ZERAF (Z) consistently achieves the lowest total energy demand among these four benchmarks in all climates, demonstrating total energy savings relative to the Typical baseline ranging from 48% (Athens) to 88% (Stockholm). The improvements offered by ZERAF over the passive

Gold standard are present but less dramatic than in the residential cases, reflecting the smaller surface area available for the ZERAF system to operate:

Warmer Climates (Z vs Co): Athens -12% (31.1 vs 35.5), Madrid -18% (16.6 vs 20.2), Milan -13% (22.7 vs 26.3).

Colder Climates (Z vs Co): Bolzano -14% (6.1 vs 7.5), Stockholm -11% (7.5 vs 9.1), Berlin -18% (8.4 vs 10.4).

These reductions confirm ZERAF's benefits even when applied to a limited area, primarily driven by optimizing heat transfer through the single exposed opaque façade section.

5.3.2 Advanced Façades Comparison in Warmer Climates

Figure 11 focuses on the warmer climates (Athens, Madrid, Milan) for the Office model, comparing Compliant (Co), Ventilated Façade Compliant (VCo), Gold (Go), Ventilated Façade Gold (VGo), INFINITE (Inf), and ZERAF (Z). Percentage changes are referenced against the Compliant (Co) baseline.

Figure 11. Heating and cooling energy demand intensity for the Office in warmer climates (Athens, Madrid, Milan) for Compliant (Co), Ventilated Façade Compliant (VCo), Gold (Go), Ventilated Façade Gold (VGo), INFINITE (Inf), and ZERAF (Z). Bars show heating (orange) and cooling (blue), with percentage improvements referenced against the Compliant (Co) baseline.

In these cooling-dominated scenarios for the office, the impact of the different advanced façades applied to the limited south opaque wall is relatively small compared to the overall loads dominated by solar gains through the large southern glazing and internal gains.

The passive Ventilated Façade options (VCo, VGo) show minimal deviation from their non-ventilated counterparts (Co, Go). VCo results in total energy changes relative to Co of -2% in Athens (39.0 vs 39.8

kWh/m²/yr), -1% in Madrid (22.9 vs 23.3 kWh/m²/yr), and 0% in Milan (31.7 vs 31.9 kWh/m²/yr). The VGo performance is virtually identical to the Go performance in all three cities (difference < 0.1 kWh/m²/yr).

The INFINITE (Inf) façade also performs almost identically to the Gold (Go) standard, with total energy differences less than 0.1 kWh/m²/yr in Athens and Madrid, and a minimal 0.1 kWh/m²/yr difference in Milan (Inf 26.0 vs Go 26.3).

The passive ventilation effect, whether in VCo, VGo, or Inf, is insufficient to cause significant changes in total energy demand when applied only to the small opaque portion of the south wall, especially when cooling loads are high due to glazing and internal gains.

ZERAF (Z) provides the most notable improvement, achieving reductions in total energy demand relative to the Compliant (Co) baseline of -22% in Athens (31.1 vs 39.8 kWh/m²/yr), -28% in Madrid (16.6 vs 23.3 kWh/m²/yr), and -28% in Milan (22.7 vs 31.9 kWh/m²/yr). Compared to the Gold standard (Go), ZERAF primarily achieves savings by reducing the cooling load:

Athens: Cooling reduced by 12% (30.9 vs 35.3 kWh/m²/yr).

Madrid: Cooling reduced by 18% (16.4 vs 20.0 kWh/m²/yr).

Milan: Cooling reduced by 14% (21.7 vs 25.1 kWh/m²/yr).

Heating loads are already minimal in these cases and show negligible change. The active control of ZERAF allows it to achieve measurable cooling energy savings (12-18% vs Gold) even with its limited application area, surpassing the negligible impact of the passive ventilated options.

5.3.3 Advanced Façades Comparison in Colder Climates

Figure 12 presents the results for the Office model in the colder climates (Bolzano, Stockholm, Berlin), comparing the same six configurations with percentage changes referenced against the Compliant (Co) baseline.

Figure 12. Heating and cooling energy demand intensity for the Office in colder climates (Bolzano, Stockholm, Berlin) for Compliant (Co), Ventilated Façade Compliant (VCo), Gold (Go), Ventilated Façade Gold (VGo), INFINITE (Inf), and ZERAF (Z). Bars show heating (orange) and cooling (blue), with percentage improvements referenced against the Compliant (Co) baseline.

In these climates, where heating loads are significant (though less dominant than in the residential cases due to high internal gains typical of offices), the performance of the passive ventilated façades applied to the limited south opaque wall presents some unexpected trends compared to the SFH and MFH results.

The VCo configuration shows a slight increase in total energy demand compared to Co, primarily due to increased heating load outweighing minimal cooling savings: +5% in Bolzano (14.5 vs 13.8 kWh/m²/yr), +1% in Stockholm (20.7 vs 20.3 kWh/m²/yr), and 0% change in Berlin (18.7 vs 18.6 kWh/m²/yr). This aligns with the expectation that passive ventilation increases heating penalties in cold climates, although the effect is marginal here. Moreover, both the VGo and INFINITE (Inf) configurations show slightly lower total energy demands compared to the standard Gold (Go) baseline in these colder climates.

The VGo configuration results in minor total energy reductions compared to Gold: -4% in Bolzano (7.2 vs 7.5 kWh/m²/yr), -6% in Stockholm (8.5 vs 9.1 kWh/m²/yr), and -5% in Berlin (9.8 vs 10.4 kWh/m²/yr). This is primarily driven by a small reduction in the heating load (e.g., Stockholm VGo H: 4.4 vs Go H: 4.9 kWh/m²/yr).

The INFINITE (Inf) façade performs very similarly to VGo, also offering slight heating savings compared to Gold and resulting in comparable minor total energy reductions relative to Gold: -3% in Bolzano (7.2 vs 7.5 kWh/m²/yr), -4% in Stockholm (8.6 vs 9.1 kWh/m²/yr), and -5% in Berlin (9.9 vs 10.4 kWh/m²/yr).

This finding – that passive ventilated façades (VGo, Inf) perform slightly better than the highly insulated, non-ventilated Gold standard in these heating-dominated office scenarios – deviates significantly from the trends observed in the SFH and MFH cases. In the residential buildings, passive ventilation consistently led to increased heating loads and higher total energy consumption compared to the Gold standard in cold climates. The reasons for this discrepancy in the Office model are not immediately clear and warrant further investigation in future studies.

Despite this unexpected result for VGo/Inf vs Go, their performance improvement relative to the Compliant (Co) baseline remains substantial (total energy reductions of 46-58%), largely reflecting the superior insulation level shared by the Gold, VGo, and INFINITE scenarios compared to Compliant.

ZERAF (Z) delivers the best performance, achieving the lowest total energy demand. The reductions relative to the Compliant (Co) baseline are significant: -55% in Bolzano (6.1 vs 13.8 kWh/m²/yr), -63% in Stockholm (7.5 vs 20.3 kWh/m²/yr), and -54% in Berlin (8.4 vs 18.6 kWh/m²/yr). ZERAF also provides further reductions compared to the Gold standard, primarily by lowering both heating and cooling loads slightly:

Heating Reduction (Z vs Go): Bolzano (-15%), Stockholm (-16%), Berlin (-16%).

Cooling Reduction (Z vs Go): Bolzano (-20%), Stockholm (-19%), Berlin (-21%).

The total energy savings relative to Gold are -19% in Bolzano, -18% in Stockholm, and -19% in Berlin. Even in these colder climates, ZERAF's active adaptation provides additional benefits over high-performance passive solutions like Gold, VGo, and INFINITE, though the overall impact is moderated by the limited surface area of application. The consistent percentage improvement across these colder climates suggests that ZERAF's benefit here relates more to optimizing insulation value and reducing residual cooling than strongly correlating with solar gain potential (unlike the residential cases), which would be another subject of future study.

5.3.4 Office Results Conclusion

In conclusion, for the Office typology, while standard envelope improvements (Typical to Gold) provide substantial energy savings, the impact of advanced façade technologies applied only to the opaque part of the south wall is less pronounced than in the fully exposed residential buildings. Façade systems with passive ventilation (VCo, VGo, Inf) show minimal benefits or even slight penalties. ZERAF, however, distinguishes itself by providing consistent, measurable reductions in both heating and cooling demands across all climates compared to the Gold standard, demonstrating the value of its active control even on a limited application area.

6 Analysis of ZERAF performance in a typical week

The preceding sections quantified the annual energy savings achieved by the ZERAF technology compared to various benchmarks. This section examines the operational dynamics of the ZERAF façade system during typical operational periods to explain the mechanisms driving these energy performance improvements. By examining detailed hourly data for typical summer and winter weeks, we compare the ZERAF system's behavior against a defined static case, focusing on indoor operative temperature, heating/cooling loads, and envelope heat transfer.

6.1 The role of the economizer in decreasing cooling loads

Before analyzing the ZERAF façade mechanisms in isolation, it is important to acknowledge the role of the economizer within the building to decrease the cooling loads. As specified in the modeling assumptions (Sections 3.1.2, 3.2.2), the Compliant and Gold performance levels (and their variants, including ZERAF) are equipped with an economizer. This function increases ventilation rates (up to 3 ACH) using cool outdoor air for "free cooling" when indoor temperatures exceed 24°C and outdoor air is at least 2°C cooler, significantly reducing mechanical cooling loads.

Simulation results show a significant difference in how the economizer function operates between the standard Gold configuration and the ZERAF configuration. For instance, Figure 13 compares the annual economizer utilization for the MFH archetype's second-floor zone. In this case, the annual heat removed by the economizer was substantially higher for the Gold case (553 kWh) than for the ZERAF case (143 kWh). Additionally, it is noteworthy that despite this lower reliance on the economizer, the ZERAF case maintained consistently lower average daily indoor temperatures during the cooling season.

This indicates that the ZERAF technology effectively minimizes overheating and heat-trapping potential by reducing heat accumulation within the building envelope, consequently requiring less frequent or intense economizer activation. However, to isolate the impact of ZERAF's façade elements (KC and ActIns)—and especially to avoid discrepancies arising from differing economizer activation patterns between the two cases—the economizer function was deactivated for both the ZERAF and static configurations during the detailed weekly analysis presented in Sections 5.2 and 5.3. This ensures a clearer evaluation of façade-driven thermal performance, eliminating variability associated with economizer control strategies.

Figure 13. Comparison of daily economizer heat removal and daily average indoor temperature for MFH second floor zone (Gold vs. ZERAF). Top panel: Summed daily heat removed by the economizer [kWh]. Bottom panel: Daily average indoor zone temperature [°C], with a 24°C threshold for the economizer control indicated. Data shown for the MFH archetype in the Milan climate.

6.2 ZERAF vs Static and Component Contributions: A typical week in summer

To gain deeper insight into how the ZERAF technology's each individual component and their combination achieve energy savings, particularly during cooling periods, this section analyzes its operational dynamics over a typical summer week (24 July to 31 July) in Milan for the middle zone of the Multi-Family House model. This analysis examines the performance by comparing the full ZERAF system against its individual components and a baseline control case. Four simulation scenarios were established:

- Static: No Kinetic Cladding (KC) or Active Insulation System (ActIns).
- KC: Only KC is operational, and ActIns fans are off.
- ActIns: Only ActIns is operational, and no KC.
- ZERAF: Both KC and ActIns are operational.

Crucially, to ensure a fair comparison focused strictly on the façade's thermal performance, the building's economizer system was deactivated for all four scenarios during this specific weekly

analysis. This prevents the free cooling effect of the economizer from influencing or masking the façade-driven results, especially when the economizer's operation will not necessarily be the same across all cases.

For the cases involving active components (KC, ActIns, and ZERAF), the adaptive façade operation begins on July 25, indicated by the vertical dashed purple line in the plots. Before this point, all cases behave identically to the Static case, i.e., neither KC nor ActIns is available in any of the cases.

Figure 14 presents the detailed hourly comparison for this summer week, while Table 16 summarizes the aggregated weekly performance metrics based on the simulation data.

Figure 14. Hourly comparison of four façade configurations (Static, KC, ActIns, and ZERAF) during a typical summer week (24–31 July) in Milan. The adaptive systems (KC and ActIns) become operational on 25 July. Top panel: Zone operative temperature comparison, showing improved thermal comfort with active façade

components. Middle panel: HVAC system heating/cooling load rates, where negative values indicate cooling demand. Bottom panel: Surface conduction through the exterior envelope, with negative values representing heat leaving the zone. ZERAF, combining KC and ActIns, demonstrates superior performance across all metrics.

Zone Operative Temperature (Top Panel, Figure 14): After the activation on July 25, all active façade configurations demonstrate improved thermal comfort compared to the Static case (red line), which shows the highest peak indoor temperatures. The KC system alone (dotted green line) provides a noticeable reduction in daytime peaks, primarily due to shading and cavity ventilation effects mitigating solar gain impact on the opaque walls. The ActIns system alone (dashed green line) also lowers peak temperatures and is particularly effective at reducing nighttime temperatures by facilitating heat rejection to the cooler exterior. The full ZERAF system (solid green line) consistently achieves the lowest indoor operative temperatures throughout the activation period, indicating a strong synergistic effect between KC and ActIns. This is also reflected in the number of hours where temperatures exceeded 26°C: 86 hours for the Static case, reduced to 76 hours by KC, further reduced to 17 hours by ActIns, and reaching the lowest duration of only 13 hours with ZERAF.

HVAC System Heating/Cooling Load (Middle Panel, Figure 14): The impact on cooling energy demand (negative values) is significant following activation. Compared to the Static case (red line), which requires the highest cooling rate, all active façade configurations reduce the cooling loads, with ActIns and ZERAF having the most pronounced impact and KC having a notable effect. Additionally, the ActIns and ZERAF configurations significantly reduce the peak cooling loads. The ZERAF system (solid green) demonstrates the most substantial benefit, requiring significantly lower cooling rates than any other case. The total weekly cooling energy demand confirms this hierarchy: 136.3 kWh for The Static case, reduced to 121.2 kWh by KC (-11% vs Static), drastically reduced to 79.1 kWh by ActIns (-42% vs Static), and achieving the lowest demand of 68.3 kWh with ZERAF (-50% vs Static). This highlights that while both components contribute significantly, their combined operation in ZERAF offers the largest cooling energy savings.

Surface Conduction through the Exterior Envelope (Bottom Panel, Figure 14): This plot illustrates the different heat management strategies employed by each façade configuration (positive values indicate heat entering the zone, negative values indicate heat leaving). The Static case (red line) shows considerable conductive heat gain (positive values) through the envelope during daytime hours. The KC system (dotted green) notably reduces this daytime conductive gain, demonstrating the effectiveness of its dynamic shading and cavity ventilation; however, it is unable to utilize the cool nighttime temperature and facilitate heat transfer outwards, resulting in conduction values generally fluctuating near zero during these periods.

The ActIns system (dashed green) also reduces daytime gain compared to the control, but its most prominent effect is dramatically increasing nighttime heat loss (significantly more negative conduction), actively releasing stored heat from the building when outdoor conditions are favorable. The ZERAF system (solid green) effectively combines the strengths of both components: it minimizes daytime heat gain, leveraging the shading and ventilation effects also seen with KC, and maximizes nighttime heat dissipation, utilizing the active heat transfer capability of ActIns. It is noteworthy that during the night, the conduction trends for the ActIns and ZERAF cases closely converge, highlighting the dominant role of the active insulation's heat purging mechanism. Conversely, during the day, their trends diverge, with ZERAF consistently rejecting more heat (showing lower or more negative conduction) than ActIns alone, demonstrating the added benefit of KC's shading and ventilation in the integrated system.

An important point is that these conduction values are calculated at the inside surface of the exterior walls (the faces adjacent to the indoor zone). Therefore, a (net) negative conduction value signifies that the interior wall surfaces are cooler than the zone air (on average), actively drawing heat out of the zone. The observation that the ZERAF configuration maintains consistently negative conduction for extended periods, even while keeping the overall zone temperature lower than the Static case (Top Panel, Figure 14), is particularly impressive, highlighting its ability to cool the building envelope and remove heat directly from the conditioned space.

The weekly total conduction energy summarizes these effects: a net heat gain of +14.9 kWh for the Static case and +0.8 kWh for KC, shifting dramatically to a substantial net heat loss of -37.4 kWh for ActIns and achieving the greatest heat rejection with -48.7 kWh for ZERAF. This demonstrates ZERAF's potent capability to actively manage envelope heat flows, effectively rejecting unwanted summer heat gain and dissipating stored heat during cooler periods.

Table 16. Summary of weekly thermal performance metrics (24–31 July) for four façade scenarios. A negative number in the total conduction energy indicates heat being removed from the zone.

Metric	Static	KC	ActIns	ZERAF
Number of Hours Operative Temperature > 26°C	86	76	17	13
Total Cooling Energy Demand [kWh]	136.3	121.2	79.1	68.3
Total Conduction Energy Through Envelope [kWh]	14.9	0.8	-37.4	-48.7

6.3 ZERAF vs Static and Component Contributions: A typical week in winter

To further detail the impact of ZERAF and its components during heating-dominated conditions, a detailed weekly analysis was conducted for a typical winter week (20–27 December) in Bolzano, characterized by significant heating requirements. Similar to the summer analysis, four scenarios were simulated:

- Static: No Kinetic Cladding (KC) or Active Insulation System (ActIns).
- KC: Only KC is operational, and ActIns fans are off.
- ActIns: Only ActIns is operational, and no KC.
- ZERAF: Both KC and ActIns are operational.

Figure 15 and Table 17 present the detailed hourly and aggregated weekly data:

Zone Operative Temperature: Throughout the week, the ZERAF configuration maintains the warmest and most stable indoor conditions. Notably, the number of hours the zone's operative temperature dropped below the comfort threshold of 19°C was lowest for ZERAF (62 hours), closely followed by ActIns (62 hours), while the Static and KC cases saw more frequent drops (65 and 64 hours, respectively).

Heating and Cooling Loads: The total heating energy required was reduced significantly by ZERAF, from 101.9 kWh in the control case to 83.8 kWh with ZERAF, representing an 18% reduction in heating demand. This improvement highlights ZERAF's capability to reduce heat losses effectively in colder conditions with solar radiation during the heating season.

Envelope Surface Conduction: Heat loss through conduction via the envelope was substantially decreased with ZERAF, from -55.5 kWh (control) to -33.4 kWh (ZERAF). This difference of 22.1 kWh demonstrates the passive heating enabled by the active insulation system.

The winter week analysis emphasizes ZERAF's adaptability and effectiveness in reducing heating demands and enhancing thermal comfort in colder climates, confirming its value as a year-round active thermal management solution.

Figure 15. Hourly comparison of four façade configurations (Static, KC, ActIns, and ZERAF) during a typical winter week (20–27 December) in Bolzano. Adaptive operation starts on 21 December. Top panel: Zone operative temperature comparison highlighting thermal stability improvements. Middle panel: HVAC system heating/cooling loads (positive values represent heating demand). Bottom panel: Surface conduction through the exterior envelope (negative values indicate heat loss).

Table 17. Summary of weekly thermal performance metrics (20–27 December) for four façade scenarios. Negative conduction values represent heat losses from the interior zone to the exterior.

Metric	Static	KC	ActIns	ZERAF
Number of Hours Operative Temperature < 19°C	65	64	62	62
Total Heating Energy Demand [kWh]	101.9	97.8	87.4	83.8
Total Conduction Energy Through Envelope [kWh]	-55.5	-50.9	-37.7	-33.4

7 Future work

While the simulation results presented in this report demonstrate the significant potential of the ZERAF technology for reducing building energy consumption across various climates and typologies, they represent preliminary findings (T.4.1: non-validated results) based on specific modeling assumptions. Several key areas warrant further investigation and development to fully understand and optimize the ZERAF system's real-world performance and impact.

7.1 Control Strategy Optimization

A critical area for future work is the refinement and optimization of the control strategies governing the interaction between (i) Kinetic Cladding (KC), (ii) the Active Insulation System (ActIns), and (iii) the operation of HVAC systems. Although the current control logic demonstrates substantial annual energy savings – even compared to ZERAF's individual components – detailed hourly analysis reveals instances where the ActIns configuration outperforms the ZERAF configuration, suggesting that ZERAF's operation is not achieving its theoretical optimum.

An example of this is observed during the daytime on June 7th in the summer week analysis (Figure 13).

Figure 16. Hourly performance comparison during a summer week (June 3-10) highlighting a control strategy anomaly on June 7th. Top: Zone Operative Temperature. Middle: HVAC Cooling Load. Bottom: Surface Conduction. On June 7th daytime, the ActIns-only configuration (dashed green) outperforms the full ZERAF system (solid green) in terms of lower operative temperature, cooling load, and heat rejection via conduction.

As seen in Figure 16, beginning around sunrise on June 7th and becoming more pronounced over the subsequent days (June 8th and 9th), the ActIns-only configuration (dashed green line) achieves lower indoor operative temperatures and requires less cooling energy compared to the full ZERAF system (solid green line), especially during daytime hours. Furthermore, the surface conduction plot shows ActIns alone dissipating more heat (more negative conduction) than ZERAF during these specific daytime periods.

This sustained underperformance of the ZERAF configuration compared to ActIns suggests a potential conflict or lack of synergy in the control strategy under these specific environment conditions. A likely hypothesis is that the KC component remained in a state (e.g., closed, limiting effective surface heat dissipation) that hindered the ActIns component's ability to dissipate heat effectively during the day (while it could), resulting in ZERAF performing worse than if the ActIns had been operating without the interference of the cladding in that specific state. Conversely, the KC might have opened while the ActIns was trying to insulate, or other non-synergistic combinations might have occurred.

While such periods are outweighed by ZERAF's overall superior performance on an annual basis, this sustained anomaly lasting several days strongly underscores the need for optimizing the control logic. Future control strategies must ensure robust synergistic operation between KC and ActIns across a wider range of dynamic conditions. This optimization could incorporate inputs such as:

Real-time HVAC system status: Adjusting façade operation based on whether the heating/cooling system is active, its current load, and energy consumption.

Occupancy data: Adapting strategies based on predicted or sensed occupant presence and potentially their comfort preferences.

Advanced control frameworks: Exploring Model Predictive Control (MPC) or machine learning-based approaches to dynamically optimize façade behavior.

7.2 Simulation Validation

A crucial next step is the calibration of the simulation models representing the ZERAF components. This will involve comparing simulation outputs from specific test scenarios with data gathered from laboratory tests on ZERAF prototypes conducted under identical, controlled conditions.

7.3 Broadening the Scope of Analysis

This report primarily focuses on quantifying the impact of ZERAF on heating and cooling energy loads at the building level. Future analyses should expand upon this preliminary work by:

- Assessing HVAC System Interaction
- Investigating the interplay of ZERAF with different internal thermal mass
- Occupant Behavior Profiles
- Assessing ZERAF's impact under future weather projections
- Assessing the impact of ZERAF applied to the existing buildings (instead of new-builts)
- Assessing the impact of ZERAF-façade orientation

8 Conclusion

This simulation study systematically evaluated the potential impact of the ZERAF active façade technology on the operational energy performance of three representative building typologies (SFH, MFH, Office) across six diverse European climates. By comparing ZERAF against standard passive envelope performance levels (Typical, Compliant, Gold) and advanced passive façade benchmarks (Ventilated Façade variants VCo/VGo, INFINITE), the following key conclusions can be drawn:

Consistent Superior Performance: ZERAF demonstrated the lowest annual heating and cooling energy demand intensity among all tested configurations for both residential typologies (SFH and MFH) across all six climates. It consistently outperformed even the highly insulated passive Gold (Passivhaus) standard, highlighting the significant benefits of active façade control.

Effectiveness in Warmer Climates: In climates with significant cooling loads (Athens, Madrid, Milan), ZERAF achieved substantial reductions in both cooling and heating demands compared to the Gold standard. This contrasts sharply with passive ventilated façades (VGo, INFINITE), which, while reducing cooling loads relative to Gold, incurred a notable heating penalty. ZERAF's integrated control of Kinetic Cladding (KC) for dynamic shading/ventilation and Active Insulation (ActIns) for potential nighttime heat rejection proved highly effective.

Effectiveness in Colder Climates: In heating-dominated climates (Bolzano, Stockholm, Berlin), ZERAF again provided the lowest total energy demand. Crucially, it reduced heating loads compared to the Gold standard, whereas passive ventilated façades (VGo, INFINITE) increased heating loads and total energy consumption due to excessive heat loss through the cavity. ZERAF's ability to dynamically maximize thermal resistance (via ActIns/closed KC) and harvest available solar gains (via open KC/ActIns heat transfer) was particularly beneficial, with performance gains over Gold correlating positively with winter solar irradiance.

Demonstrated Operational Mechanisms: The detailed weekly analyses (Section 5) confirmed ZERAF's operational principles. In summer, it actively reduced daytime heat gain and facilitated nighttime heat purging, lowering indoor temperatures and cooling loads. In winter, it minimized heat loss and effectively utilized solar gains, reducing heating demand while maintaining comfortable indoor temperatures.

Typology-Specific Impact: The energy savings achieved by ZERAF were most pronounced in the SFH and MFH typologies, where the technology was applied to all exterior opaque surfaces, with the relative improvement over the high-performance Gold standard consistently more pronounced in the SFH compared to the MFH across all six tested climates. In the Office model, where ZERAF was applied only to the opaque portion of the south façade, the relative impact was smaller, though still consistently positive, outperforming Gold and other benchmarks in all climates. The unexpected slight heating benefit observed for VGo/INFINITE over Gold in the Office model in colder climates warrants further investigation.

Potential of Active Façades: Overall, these non-validated simulation results strongly suggest that the ZERAF active façade system holds significant potential for reducing building operational energy consumption across Europe. Its ability to adapt dynamically to changing environmental conditions and actively manage heat flows allows it to overcome the inherent limitations of static passive systems, delivering superior year-round energy performance and improved thermal comfort.

Future work should focus on experimental validation of these findings, refinement of control strategies for KC and ActIns integration, investigation of the Office model anomaly, and assessment of economic feasibility and life cycle impacts. However, this initial quantification provides compelling evidence for the advancement of active façade technologies like ZERAF in the pursuit of highly energy-efficient buildings.

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9 Appendix

Table 18. Simulated Annual Energy Demand Intensities (kWh/m²/year) for the Single-Family House (SFH) by Façade Type and Climate.

Façade Type	Bolzano			Athens		
	Energy Demand Intensity (kWh/m ² /yr)					
	Heating	Cooling	Total	Heating	Cooling	Total
Typical	182.1	3.1	185.2	33.9	55.9	89.8
Compliant	52.7	0.8	53.5	7.0	24.3	31.3
V_Facade_Comp (VCo)	61.7	0.2	61.9	9.4	17.1	26.5
Gold	21.0	1.5	22.5	1.9	24.0	25.9
V_Facade_Gold (VGo)	24.6	0.6	25.2	2.2	18.5	20.7
INFINITE	26.7	0.6	27.3	2.5	18.7	21.2
ZERAF	13.6	0.2	13.8	1.1	7.7	8.8
Façade Type	Madrid			Berlin		
	Energy Demand Intensity (kWh/m ² /yr)					
	Heating	Cooling	Total	Heating	Cooling	Total
Typical	89.5	31.8	121.3	208.7	4.6	213.3
Compliant	21.4	10.9	32.3	58.8	1.4	60.2
V_Facade_Comp (VCo)	26.6	6.9	33.5	64.3	0.6	64.9
Gold	6.6	11.9	18.5	26.4	2.2	28.6
V_Facade_Gold (VGo)	7.9	7.4	15.3	28.9	1.0	29.9
INFINITE	8.8	7.5	16.3	30.8	1.0	31.8
ZERAF	4.3	3.1	7.4	25.2	0.5	25.7
Façade Type	Stockholm			Milan		
	Energy Demand Intensity (kWh/m ² /yr)					
	Heating	Cooling	Total	Heating	Cooling	Total
Typical	240.4	2.3	242.7	115.1	29.0	144.1
Compliant	73.1	0.6	73.7	32.3	12.2	44.5
V_Facade_Comp (VCo)	80.3	0.1	80.4	37.3	7.5	44.8
Gold	34.8	0.9	35.7	12.8	13.6	26.4
V_Facade_Gold (VGo)	38.1	0.4	38.5	14.8	8.9	23.7
INFINITE	40.4	0.4	40.8	16.0	9.0	25.0
ZERAF	33.7	0.2	33.9	9.2	3.5	12.7

Table 19. Simulated Annual Energy Demand Intensities (kWh/m²/year) for the Multi-Family House (MFH) by Façade Type and Climate.

Façade Type	Bolzano			Athens		
	Energy Demand Intensity (kWh/m ² /yr)					
	Heating	Cooling	Total	Heating	Cooling	Total
Typical	133.7	6.2	139.9	25.3	53.4	78.7
Compliant	48.9	0.6	49.5	8.8	17.1	25.9
V_Facade_Comp (VCo)	55.8	0.1	55.9	10.8	12.4	23.2
Gold	22.6	0.8	23.4	3.8	14.7	18.5
V_Facade_Gold (VGo)	25.4	0.2	25.6	4.1	11.4	15.5
INFINITE	27.1	0.2	27.3	4.4	11.4	15.8
ZERAF	17.4	0.1	17.5	2.5	5.4	7.9
Façade Type	Madrid			Berlin		
	Energy Demand Intensity (kWh/m ² /yr)					
	Heating	Cooling	Total	Heating	Cooling	Total
Typical	65.8	33.4	99.2	151.9	6.6	158.5
Compliant	22.3	8.0	30.3	52.9	1.1	54.0
V_Facade_Comp (VCo)	26.2	5.1	31.3	56.6	0.4	57.0
Gold	9.6	7.1	16.7	26.4	1.3	27.7
V_Facade_Gold (VGo)	10.4	4.5	14.9	28.0	0.5	28.5
INFINITE	11.2	4.5	15.7	29.5	0.5	30.0
ZERAF	7.1	1.8	8.9	25.4	0.2	25.6
Façade Type	Stockholm			Milan		
	Energy Demand Intensity (kWh/m ² /yr)					
	Heating	Cooling	Total	Heating	Cooling	Total
Typical	176.3	5.0	181.3	83.7	33.3	117.0
Compliant	64.8	0.4	65.2	30.3	9.3	39.6
V_Facade_Comp (VCo)	70.0	0.1	70.1	34.0	5.8	39.8
Gold	33.2	0.5	33.7	14.1	8.5	22.6
V_Facade_Gold (VGo)	35.6	0.1	35.7	15.5	5.5	21.0
INFINITE	37.4	0.1	37.5	16.5	5.6	22.1
ZERAF	32.3	0.0	32.3	11.6	2.0	13.6

Table 20. Simulated Annual Energy Demand Intensities (kWh/m²/year) for the Office Archetype by Façade Type and Climate.

Façade Type	Bolzano			Athens		
	Energy Demand Intensity (kWh/m ² /yr)					
	Heating	Cooling	Total	Heating	Cooling	Total
Typical	31.9	8.9	40.8	2.3	58.1	60.4
Compliant	8.6	5.2	13.8	0.7	39.1	39.8
V_Facade_Comp (VCo)	9.6	4.9	14.5	0.7	38.3	39.0
Gold	2.0	5.5	7.5	0.2	35.3	35.5
V_Facade_Gold (VGo)	1.8	5.2	7.0	0.2	35.3	35.5
INFINITE	1.9	5.3	7.2	0.2	35.3	35.5
ZERAF	1.7	4.4	6.1	0.2	30.9	31.1
Façade Type	Madrid			Berlin		
	Energy Demand Intensity (kWh/m ² /yr)					
	Heating	Cooling	Total	Heating	Cooling	Total
Typical	9.0	35.4	44.4	45.0	11.2	56.2
Compliant	1.4	21.9	23.3	11.6	7.0	18.6
V_Facade_Comp (VCo)	1.6	21.3	22.9	12.0	6.7	18.7
Gold	0.2	20.0	20.2	3.2	7.2	10.4
V_Facade_Gold (VGo)	0.2	19.9	20.1	2.9	6.9	9.8
INFINITE	0.2	19.9	20.1	3.0	6.9	9.9
ZERAF	0.2	16.4	16.6	2.7	5.7	8.4
Façade Type	Stockholm			Milan		
	Energy Demand Intensity (kWh/m ² /yr)					
	Heating	Cooling	Total	Heating	Cooling	Total
Typical	56.3	8.0	64.3	18.9	40.5	59.4
Compliant	16.4	3.9	20.3	4.6	27.3	31.9
V_Facade_Comp (VCo)	17.0	3.7	20.7	5.1	26.6	31.7
Gold	4.9	4.2	9.1	1.2	25.1	26.3
V_Facade_Gold (VGo)	4.4	4.0	8.4	1.1	24.9	26.0
INFINITE	4.6	4.0	8.6	1.1	24.9	26.0
ZERAF	4.1	3.4	7.5	1.0	21.7	22.7